

Evaluation of Effect of Preparations of *Bacillus thuringiensis* on Larval Stages of *Utetheisa pulchella* Linn.

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Abstract

Bacillus thuringiensis is used for controlling lepidopteran and dipteran pests. It kills insects primarily through the action of δ -endotoxin, a proteinous constituent produced during sporulation. It affects the insect mid gut epithelium upon ingestion. Bt insecticides are considered safe to environment with a little or no harm to natural enemies and they are considered important components in IPM programs. Various formulations Bt kurstaki are available for controlling lepidopteran pests, such as Dipel (HO-1, Abbott), Thuricide (HD-1, Sandoz), Biobit (HD-1, Novo) etc. Here we present our findings observed under laboratory conditions of temperature and relative humidity to explore the effect of Bt insecticides (Dipel, Thuricide, Bactospeine) on larval stage of *Utetheisa puchella*.

Keywords

Dipel, Thuricide, Bactospeine, *Bacillus thuringiensis*, *Utetheisa puchella*.

Introduction

Utetheisa pulchella commonly called Crimson speckled moth feeds on different types plant found in India, Pakistan Shrilanka, Bangladesh, Africa, Phillipines and Europe. It's caterpillar feeds and grow on *Crotalaria juncea*, *Crotalaria burhia* (Pandey et.al. 1971), *Crotalaria mysorensis* and *Melilotus indica* (Pandey and Chattoraj, 1974), *Gossypium* species, fiber producing plants and medicinal plants. Srivastava (1983) has reported *Utetheisa pulchella* infestation on paddy and sweet potato fields also. *Utetheisa pulchella* is reported to be resistant to common insecticides and new population are also showing resistance towards commonly used insecticides. Therefore, attention towards its control and effective management is of utmost importance. Efforts have been made in formulation of chemicals that can control pest population and alternative strategies have also been worked upon for the same. In this field insect growth regulators (as insecticides), insecticide for controlling the pest population has proved more effective than other control strategy. The bioefficacy of insect growth regulators is generally manifested during ecdysis as it disturbs the process of chitin formation, thus effecting growth and development of the insects. These insect growth regulators also produce delayed symptoms, wherein the adult fail to escape from pupa and hence cannot fly, feed and mate. These insecticides also inhibit the fertility. Progress has been made in use of improved bio-control agents such as *Bacillus thuringiensis* for controlling lepidopteran, coleopteran and dipteran pests. *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt) kills insects primarily through the action of δ -endotoxin, a proteinous constituent produced during sporulation. Upon ingestion, it affects the insect mid gut epithelium; (Hofte & whitely, 1989; Gill et.al., 1992; Navon 1993). Most conventional Bt products are based on the subspecies kurstaki. HD-1 introduced by Abbott laboratory, followed by many others, is used extensively for controlling lepidopteran pest (Navon et.al. 1990;). Various formulations of Bt kurstaki are available, such as Dipel (HO-1, Abbott), Thuricide (HD-1, Sandoz), Biobit (HD-1, Novo), javelin (NRD 12, Sandoz), and MVP (Monsato). Bt insecticides are considered safe to the environment with a little or no harm to other natural insect populations and hence are considered important components in IPM programs. The impact of above Bt products on *Utetheisa pulchella* with other chemical insecticides warrants exploration of its feasibility under IPM system. Bt insecticides are considered safe to environment with a little or no harm to other insect populations. Hence they are promising components in IPM programs.

Objective of study

The aim of present investigation is to explore the effect of bio pesticides (dipel, thuricide and bactospeine) on pest *Utetheisa pulchella*. These insecticides are of biological origin based on *Bacillus thuringiensis* and create no harm to the nontarget organisms. Present research may also helpful in increasing the use of bio pesticides as they are also safe to environment and eco-friendly.

Review of Literature

Bacillus thuringiensis is an aerobic, gram positive bacteria its produces a number of insect toxins these toxins are the S protein crystal formed during sporulation. Colorado potato beetle larvae displayed tendency to avoid feeding on Bt potato Hoy and Head (1995). Studies using *Bacillus thuringiensis*, isolate 114A in toxicity experiments against the wild population of the olive pest, *Bactrocera olea* for longevity, oviposition period, number of eggs produced and percent hatch showed decrease in all above studied parameters when treated with above isolate. Navrozidis et.al. (2000). Chandra et.al. (1999) studied the effectiveness of *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt) based products, Bioilep; Dipel, and Biobit (Bt .sub sp. kurstaki) on the third instar larvae of *Helicoverpa armigera*

in environmentally controlled conditions. The LC_{50} of Bt products, for third instar larvae of the pest insect were 0.114, 0.211 and 0.213 percent respectively and for the exposed period of 48 hours and for the post exposure period (till pupation) the LC_{50} were 0.087, 0.186 and 0.159 percent. At all concentrations Bt products had adverse effect on growth and development of the pest, increased larval mortality. Nault et.al. (2000) examined the feeding, development and survival to adulthood of Colorado potato beetle after exposing large number of larvae to *Bacillus thuringiensis*. They observed that the third instar larvae on plants after a Bt application showed decreased food intake and 4th instars consumed only 50 per cent as much foliage as those fed with untreated leaves. Chaturvedi and et.al (2018) Studies on the effect of different formulations of *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Dipel, Thuricide and Bactospeine) on the growth and development of *Utetheisa pulchella*.

Methodology

Male and female *Utetheisa pulchella* (Lepidoptera; Arctidae) were collected in the first week of August. Moths are medium sized with a wing expanse of about 4 cm. Male and females were separated by observing slender and tapering abdomen for males whereas, abdomen of female is wider and stumpy. The hairy caterpillar of *Utetheisa pulchella* feeds on leaves, buds, flowers and seed capsules of *Crotolaris juncea*, *Crotolaris mysorensis*, *Crotolaris burhea*, *Melilotus indica* and *Heliotropium indicum*. The hairy caterpillars feed on leaves, buds, flowers and seed capsules of *C. juncea*, *C. mysorensis*, *C. burhea*, *Melilotus indica* and *Heliotropium indicum*. Its infestation in paddy and sweet potato fields with mild damage has also been reported by Srivastava, (1983). Female lays about 130—360 eggs during her life span. The eggs are deposited in clusters of 2-7, sometimes individually on tender leaves, buds, flowers and shoot of host plant. The egg stage lasts for 2-3 days. The newly hatched larva is dark grey with orange and faint pale lines on dorsal side, measuring about 2mm. in length. The full grown larva measuring 2-5 to 2-8 cm in length is velvety black in color with reddish brown head. Its back is covered blotchy dark red and whitish spots in the middle and sides are characterized by tubercles which bear black and brown hairs pointing laterally and upwards. The larval period lasts for 20 to 25 days during which larva undergoes moulting four times resulting in five instars during this period.

Laboratory Stock Of The Pest:

A laboratory stock of the test insect was maintained in the laboratory to ensure its regular supply of different development stages in a large number for different studies during the investigation. Moths, male and females obtained from the field & maintained in glass chimneys having twenty percent sugar solution with *Crotolaria* leaves. Eggs obtained from them were kept as such for hatching. Large petridishes were used for hatching of egg with continuous food supply to obtain different instars of larvae. Twenty larvae per petridish upto second instar stage were collected and then 5 larvae were transferred in each petridish. Now full grown larvae were transferred in pneumatic troughs for pupation. Pupae, thus obtained were kept for emergence of months.

The commercial preparations of *Bacillus thuringiensis* against *Utetheisa pulchella* used in this study were :

Dipel wettable powder containing 25×10^9 viable spores per gram of final product of *Bacillus thuringiensis* var. Kurstaki (Serotype 3a, b strain HD-1).

Thuricide H.P. wettable powder containing 30×10^6 viable spores of *Bacillus thuringiensis* var. Kurstaki (serotype 3a, b strain HD-1) per gram of final product.

Bactospeine containing 1×10^8 viable spores of *Bacillus thuringiensis* (serotype -1) per gram of final product.

One gram of Dipel, Thuricide HP and Bactospeine were mixed separately in 100ml of distilled water that gave the concentration of one percent, from this, other concentrations were prepared by serial dilution method. The concentrations were applied against *Utetheisa pulchella* in the studies included 0.05, 0.10, 0.50, 0.75, and 1.0 percent. Residual film treatment method and Leaf dip treatment method are the methodology used in present investigation. In Residual film treatment method small and uniform size of leaf were exposed to a thin film of residue of a concentration of a particular bacterial preparation. For obtaining the thin film of bacterial preparation as residue, about 10ml of a concentration of bacterial preparation was poured in petridish (10 cm dia.) and the petridish was tilted in different ways to spread the bacterial preparation on the whole floor area of the petridish and its raised periphery. This led to the formation of thin film of a concentration of bacterial preparation in the petridish as residue. Adults were left in petridishes having thin film of the bacterial preparation for 24 hours. The petridishes were covered by thin muslin cloth to prevent the escape of the adults. Such treated adults were employed in the different experiments as described later on. Control experiments were also set up to evaluate and compare the findings of different experiments. Studies presented in this investigation were conducted experimentally under laboratory conditions of temperature and relative humidity and investigation is based on the effect of bacterial preparation on fecundity and fertility. The reduction in the fecundity was calculated following the formula of Chamberlain (1962) as detailed below:

The sterility was calculated following the formula of Abbot (1925) as detailed below:

$$\% \text{reduction in fecundity} = \frac{\text{Eggs laid in normal} - \text{Eggs laid in test}}{\text{Eggs laid in normal}} \times 100$$

The sterility was calculated following the formula of Abbot (1925) as detailed below:

$$\% \text{ net sterility} = \frac{\% \text{ sterility in test} - \% \text{ sterility in normal}}{100 - \% \text{ sterility in normal}} \times 100$$

Result and Discussion

Effect of dipel on reproduction under leaf dips method:

The treatment by leaf dip method with any strength of the dipel reduced the fecundity significantly (P<0.01). The fecundity in response to treatment with different strengths of this microbial preparation varied from 42.4 to 128.4 eggs/female and the analysis of variance revealed that 0.05 and 0.10 percent affected that the fecundity identical and that among concentrations from 0.50 to 1.00 percent, the fecundity differed with the different concentrations, showing indirect proportionality to the concentration of the dipel. The adult treatment with any concentration by leaf dip method reduced the fertility of the *Utetheisa pulchella*, the percentage of eggs hatched per female reduced significantly (P<0.05). in response to different concentrations of the dipel applied through leaf dip method, the fertility varying from 10.3 to 54.4 percent and decreasing with the strength dependent on the concentration of the dipel (P<0.05). Every concentration of the Dipel applied by leaf dip method, prolongs the incubation period (P<0.05). The duration of the egg stage, varying from 3.34 to 5.40 days, differed with the concentration (P<0.05). The concentrations 0.05, 0.10, 0.50, 0.75 percent affected the incubation period as compared to 1.0 percent concentration, that cause more delay i.e. 5.40 days. The reduction in the fecundity of the moth under the leaf dip treatment, varied from 39.2 or 79.0 percent among different concentration of the dipel and exhibiting indirect proportionality to the concentration, was affected differently by different concentrations (P<0.05). Further, the net sterility which varied from 7.76 to 87.37 percent among different concentrations under leaf dip treatment differed significantly from concentration to concentration and it also increases with increase in the concentration. Exactly in the same way, the percent control over the reproduction under the influence of different concentration of the dipel, varying from 50.1 to 93.0 percent and increasing with the advancing concentration depends on the strength of the dipel applied (P<0.05).(Table-1)

Table 1 Effect of Dipel on fecundity and fertility in *Utetheisa pulchella* Linn

Mode of Treatment	Concentration (N)	No. of egg laid by female	No. of egg Hatched	Hatched %	Incubation Period
LDM	0.05	128.4±3.48	69.8±3.68	54.4	3.34±0.62
	0.10	126.4±3.58	63.8±4.24	50.3	3.56±0.42
	0.50	110.3±2.69	44.3±2.78	40.2	3.92±0.12
	0.75	98.12±3.76	28.1±4.32	28.6	3.94±0.22
	1.00	42.4±2.24	4.3±1.48	10.3	5.40±0.12
RFM	0.05	131.4±2.47	74.5±2.61	56.7	3.33±0.51
	0.10	122.5±3.30	65.4±3.96	53.4	3.44±0.31
	0.50	111.2±2.45	48.3±2.52	43.5	3.87±0.23
	0.75	89.4±3.28	19.1±3.73	21.4	3.97±0.13
	1.00	51.3±2.49	7.7± 1.31	15.2	5.06±0.11
	Control	346.41±4.28	310.3± 4.18	89.6	2.98 ±0.28

Table 2

Per cent reduction in fecundity, per cent net sterility and per cent control over reproduction in *Utetheisa pulchella* Linn caused by Dipel under different mode of treatment

Mode of Treatment	Concentration (N)	% Reduction in fecundity	% Net Sterility	% Control Over reproduction
LDM	0.05	39.2	7.76	50.1
	0.10	45.0	95.62	56.8
	0.50	62.3	40.34	78.9
	0.75	70.7	56.72	90.6
	1.00	79.0	87.37	93.0
RFM	0.05	38.9	10.63	47.7
	0.10	44.4	40.37	54.4
	0.50	56.3	52.72	73.9
	0.75	68.4	58.64	88.9
	1.00	73.6	81.46	94.9

Effect of dipel or reproduction under residue film method:

The fecundity (eggs/female) was reduced by residue film of any concentration of the dipel applied to the adult (P<0.05). The fecundity varied from 51.3 to 131.4 eggs/female in response to treatment with residue films of different concentrations and appearing to decrease with the advancing concentrations of dipel and tending to be indirectly proportional to the concentration differed significantly with the concentrations. Any of these concentration (0.05 to 1.0%) caused reduction in fecundity significantly (P<0.05). Further, every concentration of the dipel applied as residue film lead to reduction in hatching of eggs, In response to treatment of adults with dipel as residue films , the hatchability of eggs, varying from 15.2 to 56.7 percent among different concentrations and tending indirectly proportional to the concentrations was affected differently by different concentration as residue film (P<0.05). The egg stage, incubation period, was also affected significantly by every concentration of dipel applied to adults under the residue film method (P<0.05). This period varying from 3.33 to 5.06 days among different concentrations and increasing with the increasing concentration of dipel (P<0.05). (Table-2) Every concentration of the dipel method applied earlier as residue film to adults caused reduction in the fecundity which, varying from 38.9 to 73.6 percent among the different concentrations of this microbial preparation and exhibiting direct relationship to the concentration, was detected by chi-square to differ from concentration to concentration of the dipel applied earlier to adults (P<0.05). Further, in response to residue film treatment to female with different concentrations of the dipel the per cent net sterility and percent control over reproduction, varying from 10.63 to 81.46 percent and 47.7 to 94.9 percent respectively and increasing with the increasing concentrations, was affected differently by these concentrations (P<0.05).

Effect of thuricide on reproduction under the leaf dip method :

The treatment by leaf dip method with every concentration of the thuricide delayed the sexual maturity (P<0.05). the per-oviposition period of the treated adults varied from 3.08 to 3.72 days In response to different concentrations of the thuricide and appeared to be directly proportional to the concentrations applied (P<0.05). All of these concentrations also affect the oviposition period which varied from 2.78 to 5.24 days among different concentrations of the thuricide applied by leaf dip method and it decreased with the increasing concentration. The analysis of variance test revealed that under leaf dip method of treatment, the oviposition period depended on the concentration of the thuricide (P<0.05). The females treatment with all the concentrations of thuricide by leaf dip method reduced its fecundity proportionality (P<0.05). When females treated by leaf dip method with different concentrations of thuricide, the number of eggs laid by a female, varying 58.4 to 181.3 eggs. Further, the female treated by leaf dip method with different concentrations of the thuricide caused less fertility as compared the untreated female (P<0.05). The percentage of eggs hatched, varied from 18.2 to 58.2 percent among different concentrations, exhibiting decrease in hatching with the increase in concentration. Furthermore, the treatment of the female with any concentration of thuricide by leaf dip method prolonged the incubation period (P<0.05) which varied from 3.42 to 4.62 days in response to different concentrations and depended significantly on the concentration (P<0.05), exhibiting increase in the egg stage with increasing concentrations of thuricide. (Table-3) The females treatment by leaf dip method with any concentration of thuricide caused reduction in fecundity, net sterility and control over the reproduction. The reduction in fecundity varied from 36.1 to 74.4 percent. Likewise, the net sterility also varies from 6.76 to 71.37 percent and also control over the reproduction, varying from 44.2 to 94.8 percent. All these observation exhibit direct proportionality to concentration (P<0.05).

Table 3

Effect of Thuricide on fecundity and fertility in *Utetheisa pulchella* Linn

Mode of Treatment	Concentration (N)	No. of egg laid by female	No. of egg Hatched	Hatched %	Incubation Period
LDM	0.05	131.3±2.26	76.4±2.82	58.2	3.42±0.78
	0.10	128.3±3.63	67.4±3.46	52.6	3.54±0.34
	0.50	100.4±4.74	50.5±3.72	50.3	3.62±0.28
	0.75	192.7±2.52	19.1±3.10	20.7	3.85±0.17
	1.00	58.4±3.18	10.6±3.28	18.2	4.62±0.18
RFM	0.05	137.2±2.32	79.9±3.46	58.3	3.23±0.62
	0.10	130.4±2.48	69.7±3.52	53.5	3.52±0.38
	0.50	101.7±2.32	51.2±1.80	50.4	3.83±0.22
	0.75	097.9±2.78	23.1±3.41	23.7	3.87±0.18
	1.00	64.6±3.47	13.1±2.72	20.4	4.50±0.13
	Control	346.4±28	310.3±4.18	89.6	2.98 ± 0.28

Effect of thuricide on reproduction under residue film method :

The female treated with any concentration of the thuricide as residue film increase the pre-oviposition period than that of the untreated females (P<0.05). In response to residue film treatment of adults with different concentrations of this microbial preparation, the pre-oviposition period varied from 3.06 to 3.68 days, was affected significantly by these concentrations (P<0.05). likewise, every concentration of this bacterial preparation affected oviposition period significantly (P<0.05). In response the female's treatment by residue film of different concentrations of the thuricide, the duration of egg laying, varying from 2.46 to 5.25 days and exhibiting direct relationship to the concentration, differed significantly with applied strength (P<0.05). The female treatment with residue films of different concentrations of the thuricide caused reduction in fecundity (P<0.05). When females treated with residue film of different concentrations of thuricide, the number of eggs laid by a femals, varying from 64.6 to 137.2 eggs. Number of eggs exhibited indirect proportionality to the concentration. As regards the effect of residue films of different concentrations of thuricide on the fertility i.e., the percent eggs hatched/female, varying from 20.4 to 58.3 and decreasing with the increasing concentration, differed significantly with the residue films of different concentrations of the thuricide applied as residue film to adults on the incubation period, the duration of egg stage varied from 3.23 to 4.50 days among different concentrations and appeared to increase with increasing concentrations of thuricide. The statistical analysis revealed that the different concentrations affected incubation period significantly (P<0.05). Further, in response to residue film treatment of adults with different strengths of the thuricide the reduction of fecundity, net sterility and control over reproduction, varying from 37.2 to 72.6 from 5.92 to 72.56 and 45.1 to 93.2 percent respectively and showing direct proportionality to the concentration, differed significantly with different concentration of thuricide. (Table-4)

Table 4

Per cent reduction in fecundity, per cent net sterility and per cent control over reproduction in *Utetheisa pulchella* Linn caused by Thuricide under different mode of treatment

Mode of Treatment	Concentration (N)	% Reduction in fecundity	% Net sterility	% Control Over reproduction
LDM	0.05	36.1	6.76	44.2
	0.10	42.7	34.36	53.6
	0.50	56.5	36.42	73.2
	0.75	67.4	51.36	85.2
	1.00	74.4	71.37	94.8
RFM	0.05	37.2	5.92	45.1
	0.10	42.1	34.42	52.5
	0.50	59.0	51.76	74.2
	0.75	66.0	62.43	83.4
	1.00	72.6	72.56	93.2

Effect of bactospeine on reproduction under leaf dip method :

The treatment of the female with any concentration of the bactospeine prolonged the pre-oviposition period remarkably (P<0.05) and under such method of treatment with different concentrations of this microbial preparation, the pre-oviposition period varied from 2.62 to 3.66 days and tended to be directly proportional with the concentration.

Bactospeine exerted prolonging influence significantly ($P < 0.05$). The females treatment with any concentration of the bactospeine by leaf dip method also affected the oviposition period significantly ($P < 0.05$) and, In response to female's treatment with different strengths of the bactospeine, the oviposition period varying from 3.30 to 8.29 days and tending to be indirectly proportional to the concentration differed from concentration to concentration significantly ($P < 0.05$) Further, every concentration of bactospeine applied by leaf dip method caused considerable reduction in the fecundity as compared the fecundity of the untreated females ($P < 0.05$). In this context the results revealed that the different concentrations of this bacterial preparation caused a female to lay 60.4 to 131.3 eggs which depends statistically on the strength of bactospeine ($P < 0.05$) and decreased with the advancing concentration. The leaf dip method treatment with any concentration reduced the percentage of hatching of eggs also. In response to different concentrations of the bactospeine applied by leaf dip method, hatching of eggs varies from 21.2 to 61.4 percent, decreasing with the increasing strength depends on the concentration of the bactospeine ($P < 0.05$) the influence of different concentrations of the bactospeine under leaf dip method treatment, on the incubation period was affected differently ($P < 0.05$). Incubation period varies from 3.10 to 4.87 days, prolongs with advance concentrations of bactospeine. The leaf dip administration of different concentrations induced 27.4 to 68.1 percent reduction in the fecundity which differing significantly with the concentration of this bacterial preparation ($P < 0.05$) the reduction in the fecundity increased with the increasing concentrations of bactospeine. In the same way, the net sterility varies from 11.46 to 56 percent among females treated by leaf dip method with different concentrations. It was also observed that the sterility increases with the advancing concentration, differed from concentration to concentration significantly ($P < 0.05$). like the reduction in fertility and sterility , the percent control over the reproduction also varies i.e. from 34.0 to 92.2 percent and increasing with the advancing concentration, differed significantly, from concentration ($P < 0.05$). (Table-5)

Table 5

Effect of Bactospeine on fecundity and fertility in *Utetheisa pulchella* Linn

Mode of Treatment	Concentration (N)	No. of egg laid by female	No. of egg Hatched	Hatched %	Incubation Period
LDM	0.05	131.3±2.10	80.6±2.88	61.4	3.10±0.28
	0.10	128.4±2.26	67.0±1.46	52.2	3.12±0.48
	0.50	100.3±3.38	50.1±3.44	50.0	3.23±0.13
	0.75	90.6±6.38	31.1±1.78	34.4	3.43±0.35
	1.00	60.4±3.38	12.8±2.56	21.2	4.87±0.23
RFM	0.05	133.6±3.30	83.5±2.81	62.5	3.10±0.43
	0.10	140.7±3.23	74.8±2.42	53.2	3.11±0.18
	0.50	100.6±5.30	51.7±2.37	51.4	3.13±0.13
	0.75	92.8±2.42	35.4±2.42	38.2	3.32±0.32
	1.00	77.7±3.14	18.0±2.49	23.2	4.80±0.43
	Control	3464±4.28	310.3±4.18	89.6	2.98 ± 0.28

Effect of bactospeine on reproduction under residue film method:

The residue film of any concentration of the bactospeine applied to the female delayed the sexual maturity significantly ($P < 0.05$). In response to the females treatment with residue films of different concentrations of this bacterial preparation, the pre-oviposition period, varying from 2.54 to 3.46 days, tended to prolong with the advancing concentration. But the statistical analysis revealed that the concentrations from 0.05 to 0.10 percent caused significantly less prolongation in pre-oviposition period as compared the one percent concentration ($P < 0.05$). Similarly, the residue film of every concentration of the bactospeine also affected the oviposition period significantly ($P < 0.05$). This period, varying from 2.54 to 5.36 days among different concentrations of this bacterial preparation applied as residue film and decreasing with the increasing concentration, was detected to differ with the concentration of bactospeine applied to adults ($P < 0.05$). The residue film of every concentration of the bactospeine applied to the female reduced considerably her fecundity ($P < 0.05$). In response to the female's treatment with residue films of different concentrations of this microbial preparation, the fecundity varied, from 77.7 to 133.6 eggs/female and tending to decrease with the advancing concentration, depended significantly on the concentration of bactospeine. Further, every concentrations of the bactospeine applied as residue film lead to reduction in hatching of eggs. In response to treatment of adults with different concentrations of bactospeineas residue films, the hatchability of eggs, varying from 23.2 to 62.5 percent among different concentrations and tending indirectly proportional to the concentration was affected differently with the increasing concentrations of the residue film ($P < 0.05$). Different concentrations of bactospeine applied as residue film to adults prolonged the incubation period as compared to the non- treatment condition ($P < 0.05$). In response to adults treatment with residue films of different concentrations of this bacterial preparation, the incubation period varies from 3.10 to 4.80 days among these concentrations. The incubation period (3.10 to 3.13 days) was affected a like by 0.75 and 1.0 percent

concentrations, of course, with more prolongation ($P < 0.05$). Further, in response to adults treatment with residue films of different concentrations of the bactospeine the reduction in fecundity, net sterility and control over the reproduction varying from 26.7 to 66.0 percent, from 12.75 to 59.32 percent and from 34.2 to 90.4 percent respectively and increasing with the increasing concentration, differed significantly with concentrations of the residue film of this microbial preparation ($P < 0.05$). (Table-6) The microbial preparations are high toxic compounds which induced sterility consequently, help in control of the pest population by reducing the fecundity and fertility. In his investigation, every microbial preparation, screened against *Utetheisa pulchella* found effective in causing sterility even at their lowest concentrations. These induce sterility by reducing the fecundity and by decreasing the viability of the eggs laid by a female. The results reveal that the fecundity decrease with the increase in concentrations. The results also show that under the influence of the bacterial preparation, the fertility decreases distinctly with the advancing concentrations and the data pertaining to the percent reduction in fecundity and percent net sterility confirm the above facts. From the data, it is proved that dipel under leaf dip treatment cause maximum decline in the fecundity. However, the related data on the percent reduction in the fecundity shows clearly that there is indirect proportionality between the reduction in the fecundity and concentrations of the thuricide and bactospeine. This trend is also evinced by the data relating to the percent caused by different concentrations of thuricide and bactospeine under the residue film method of treatment. Under residue film treatment also, the reduction in the number of the eggs laid by a female and the hatchability of the laid eggs are distinctly concentration development, these decrease with the increasing concentrations of the bacterial preparations. The trend is clearly witnessed by the data on the percent reduction in fecundity and percent net sterility. Under the leaf dip method at 1.00 percent concentration the dipel induce about 87.37 percent sterility whereas at the same concentration, the thuricide and bactospeine induce about 71.37 and 56.64 percent net sterility respectively, controlling the reproduction to the extent of of 92.2 to 94.8 percent.

Table 6

Per cent reduction in fecundity, per cent net sterility and per cent control over reproduction in *Utetheisa pulchella* Linn caused by Bactospene under different mode of treatment

Mode of Treatment	Concentration (N)	% Reduction in fecundity	% Net sterility	% Control Over reproduction
LDM	0.05	27.4	11.44	34.0
	0.10	31.1	15.76	44.1
	0.50	45.0	26.43	63.2
	0.75	59.4	32.72	79.8
	1.00	68.1	56.54	92.2
RFM	0.05	26.7	12.75	34.2
	0.10	30.5	18.75	42.9
	0.50	42.0	20.62	60.3
	0.75	58.7	42.76	77.8
	1.00	66.0	59.32	90.4

The reports are also available in the literature that the bacterial preparation help in control of the lepidopterous pest population by reducing the fecundity and fertility. Jaques and Fox (1960), Heimpel (1961); Kulshrestha *et.al.* (1965); Dulmage and Martinez (1973); Govindrajan *et.al.* (1975); West *et.al.* (1997), Chandra *et.al.* (1999) Siegfried *et.al.* (2000) and Nault *et. al.* (2000) also worked the effect of the microbial preparations on the development of different insects. As per results of this investigation, *Utetheisa pulchella*, a lepidopterous pest, respond fairly well at 1.0 percent concentration to the bacterial preparations applied by leaf dip method or topically. With this concentration every bacterial preparation induces more than 50 percent sterility. And these findings support the works of above workers. The bacterial preparations applied through leaf dip method and residue film treatment affect the pre-oviposition and oviposition period. The pre-oviposition period prolongs even with 0.05 percent concentration of any microbial preparation. This indicates that a microbial preparation delays the sexual maturity, increases with the increasing concentration of bacterial preparation. In context of the delay in sexual maturity, considering influence of 1.0 percent concentration, the different microbial preparations may be arranged as dipel, thuricide and bactospeine in descending order. Like the pre-oviposition period, each microbial preparation even at its lowest concentration (0.05 percent) affects the oviposition period too and, this period decreases with the increasing concentration. Since the decreased oviposition period is associated with the decreased fecundity and fertility, this fact supports that every bacterial preparation retards or inhibits the oviposition. Results show that each microbial preparation has potential to increase the incubation period. Each concentration of dipel, thuricide and bactospeine exert influence on the incubation period. However, 0.75 and 1.0 percent concentration of different microbial preparations exert more influence of incubation period. The different concentrations of microbial preparation cause proportionate increase in the incubation period depending on their strength. Dipel (1.0% concentration) under leaf dip treatment extends the incubation period up to 5.40 days while under natural condition it was noted only 2.98

days. The above facts suggest that the bacterial preparations lower the speed of the embryonic development which becomes more and slower with the progressive increase in the strength of the bacterial preparation.

The literature reveals that among lepidopterous pests, the treatment by leaf dip method of different insecticides has led to the adverse effect on reproduction i.e., it leads to the sterility with different levels of success Howland *et.al.* (1965), Bobaye and Carman (1975), Flint and Smith (1977), Wright *et.al.* (1980), Navon *et.al.* (1994), Trisyono and Whalon (1997), Siegfried *et.al.* (2000), Navrozidis *et.al.* (2000), Nault *et.al.* (2000); and Chaturvedi R. *et.al.* (2018). Over results also indicate that when bacterial preparations are administered orally in adults, they are able to induce the sterility which exhibits direct proportionality to their concentration. At 1.0 percent concentration all the three bacterial preparations are able to cause very high sterility but not cent per cent. At this concentration their sterility differs among them and on this basis, these can be arranged as dipel (87.37%), thuricide (71.37%) and bactospeine (56.54%) in descending order. However, in case of all the bacterial preparations, there is a progressive increase in the sterility with the advancing concentrations which decrease the fecundity and fertility accordingly. As per our results, at 1.00 percent concentration of a microbial preparation which induces very high sterility, the longevity of the adults is very much reduced.

Conclusion

As per results of this investigation, *Utetheisa pulchella* respond fairly well at 1.0 percent concentration to the bacterial preparations applied by leaf dip method. At this concentration every bacterial preparation induces more than 50 percent sterility. The bacterial preparations are high toxic compounds that induced sterility and help in control of the pest population by reducing the fecundity and fertility. The three bacterial preparations used under this investigation are able to control the reproduction in *Utetheisa pulchella* to the extent of 90.4 to 94.9 percent at 1.0 percent concentration so at 1.0 percent concentration the dipel is the most effective bacterial preparation and bactospeine that exert similar influence in controlling the reproduction is the least effective one under residue film method of treatment. However, the dipel is most effective under leaf dip method of treatment. Thuricide is also able to control the reproduction in *Utetheisa pulchella* to the extent of about 95 percent. The comparative sterilizing effect of a bacterial preparation under both methods of treatment is quite distinct at 1.0 percent concentration. The results pertaining to the percent sterility induced by a bacterial preparation, suggest that dipel thuricide and bactospeine are more effective under leaf dip administration in adults than its application as residue film method to adults.

References

- Hofte, H. Whiteley H.R. (1989); *Insecticidal crystal proteins of Bacillus thuringiensis*. *Microbial Rev.* 53: 242-255.
- Hoy, C.W., Head, G (1995). *Correlation between behavioral and physiological responses to transgenic potatoes containing Bacillus thuringiensis δ -endotoxin in Leptinotara decemlineata (Coleoptera : chrysomelidac.)* *J. Econ. Ent.* 88 (3): 480-486.
- Gill S.S., Cowles E.A. Pietrantonio P.V. (1992). *The mode of action of Bacillus thuringiensis endotoxins*. *Annu. Rev. Entomol.* 37: 615-636.
- Chandra, A. Kaushik, N.C., Gupta, G. P. (1999). *Studied of Bacillus thuringiensis on growth and development of Hekicoverba armigara*. *Hubber Annl. Pl. port. Sci.* 7(2): 154-158.
- Nault, B.A., Costa, S.D. and Kennedy, G.G. (2000). *Colorado potato beetle (coleopteran : chrysomelidae) Feeding, development and Survival to adult hood after continuous exposure to Bacillus thuringiensis sub spp. tenebrionis treated potato foliage from the field* *J.Eco.Ent.* 93 (1): 149-156.
- Navrozidis, E.T., Vasara, E. Karamanlidou, G.K. Salpiggidis; and Koliais, S.I. (2000). *Biological control of Bactocera oleae (Diptera tephritidae) using Bacillus thuringiensis isolate* *J. Econ.Ent.*, 93 (6): 1657-1661.
- Pandey, S.N.; Pnadey, Y.D. and Kaul C.C., (1971). *An alternate host plant of Utetheisa pulchella L (Lep.Arctiidae L) Indian J. Ent.* 32 (2): 277.
- Pandey, P.N. and Chattoraj, A.N. (1974). *Host selection of Utetheisa pulchella Linn (Lep: Arctiidae), Dtsch Ent. Z., 21 (1-III): 179-192.*
- Srivastava, P.C. (1983). *Population Dynamics, Eco behavior and Energy utilization of Utetheisa pulchella Linn. (Lepidoptera: Arctiidae). A Thesis submitted at Kanpur University, Kanpur, India.*
- Jaques, R.P. and Fox, J.S. (1960). *The influence of stickers on the effectiveness oof spray of Bacillus thuringiensis Berliner and Bacillus entomocides, heimpel and Angus. J. Insect . Pathol., 2 L 17-23.*
- Heimpel, A.M. (1961). *Pathogenicity of Bacillus cereus, Frankland and Bacillus thuringiensis for several species larvae. J. invertebrate Pathology.* 3: 271-273.
- Govindrajan, R. , Jauraj, S. and Narayanan, K. (1975). *Observation on the nature of resistance in Spodoptera litura (F.0)(Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) to infection by Bacillus thuringiensis Berliner Indian. J. Exp. Biology.* 13: 548-550.
- Kulshreshtha, J.P. sanghi, P.K and Ravindranath V. (1965). *Microbial control of castor semilooper, Achaea janta L. Indian J. Ent.* 27: 353-354.
- Dulmage, H.T. and Martinez, E. (1973). *The effect of continuous exposure to low concentration of δ -endotoxin of Bacillus thuringiensis on the development of tobacco bud worm, Heliothis virescens. J. invertebrate Pathology.* 22: 14-22.
- Siegfried, B.D., , Spencer, T. and Nearman, J. (2000). *Baseline susceptibility of the corn Earworm (Lep : Noctuidae) the cry IAb toxin from Bacillus thuringiensis. J.*

Eco. Ent. 93, (4): 1265-1268.

16. Howland, A.F.; Vall P and Henneberry, T.J. (1965). Effect of chemosterilants on fertility of cabbage looper. *J. Eco. Ent.* 58: 635-637.
17. Bobaye, S.O and Carman, G.E (1975). Effect of insect growth regulator with juvenile hormone activity on the development of the California red Scale. *J. Eco. Ent.* 68 (4): 472 – 473.
18. Flint, H.M. and Smith, R.L. (1977). Laboratory evaluation of TH 60-40 against pink boll worm. *J. Eco. Ent.* 70 (1): 51.
19. Abdel-Ghany, A.A., Negam, S.E. and Saleh, A.A (1985). Morphological and biological impact of certain I.G.Rs on larvae and pupae of the Egyptian cotton leaf worm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd). *J. Agric. Sci.* 10 (1): 286-291.
20. Navon A, Klein M, Braun S (1990). *Bacillus thuringiensis* Potency bioassays against *Heliothis armigera*, *Earias insulna* and *Spodoptera littoralis* larvae based on standardized diets. *J. Invertebrate Pathology.* 55: 387-393.
21. Navon, A., Ishaaya, I., Baum, D., Ben Ari, Z., Braun, S., Yablonski, S. Karen, S. (1994). Activity of *Bacillus thuringiensis* preparations for control of the vine moth *Lobesia botrana*. *Alon-Hanotea*, 48 (8) 360-366.
22. Trisyono, A., Whalon, ME, (1997). Fitness costs of resistance to *Bacillus thuringiensis* in Colorado potato beetle (Coleoptera : Chrysomelidae). *J. Eco. Entomol.* 90 (4) 834-841.
23. Chaturvedi, R. and Gupta, A.K. (2018). Studies on the effect of different formulations of *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Dipel ,Thuricide and Bactospeine) on the growth and development of *Utetheisa pulchella* Linn. (Lepidoptera: Arctidae). *Trends in Biosciences.* 11(33) Print ISSN No.0974-8431, 3731-3740.